

The Sanskrit Yasna

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Zoroastrianism, Parsis (India), Text, Zoroastrian prayer, Zoroastrian liturgy, Sanskrit version, Sanskrit literature

The Yasna is the Zoroastrian long liturgy. Originally composed in Avestan, it was then translated into Pahlavi and some comments to the text were added. Then, the text was brought to India by the Parsi community and, presumably between the 12th and the 14th century, further translated into Sanskrit. The Sanskrit text includes many layers, namely a proper translation of the original text of the Yasna, based however on the Pahlavi version, with occasional direct reference to the original Avestan text; the translation into Sanskrit of some Pahlavi comments to the text; original Sanskrit comments, added to explain further the Zoroastrian concepts and adapt them to the Indian sociocultural environment. Finally, a few Sanskrit ritual instructions were added to the text. The Sanskrit version has never had a ritual value, but it is in any case interesting from a religious point of view. In fact, the significant terms of the Zoroastrian cult are rendered with meaningful terms belonging to other religious traditions such as Hinduism, Buddhism and, above all, Jainism. The Jaina environment of Gujarat has deeply influenced the Sanskrit version of the Yasna: for instance, the script, the so-called Parsi Nāgarī, is very close to the Jaina Nāgarī; the palaeography is close to the Jaina one, too; the text includes graphical elements which recalls the ones present in Jaina manuscripts, etc. A systematic translation project is recognisable behind the Sanskrit text, whose compilation was influenced by both Indian regional features and the Zoroastrian tradition. In the translation process, the passage from one language to the other implies the adaptation of all the formal and semantic aspects of terms and expressions. In this case, the passage went through two steps, first from Avestan to Pahlavi and then from Pahlavi to Sanskrit. The translators into Sanskrit were philologists ante litteram, who carried out a refined work of Indo-Iranian comparative philology. Finally, the geographical settlement of the Parsi community in (north-)western India, a land which has always been characterised by religious and cultural syncretism, has for sure encouraged such kind of refined study and comment to the text. There are still many open questions and the reason of the translation into Sanskrit is not clear, since the Parsi ritual language has always been Avestan and their mother tongue Gujarati. Were they trying to reach out other Indian communities and promote themselves at court? Were they providing a well-known Indian format to the Parsi community itself? The Sanskrit text of the Yasna is therefore not useful on a ritual level, but it may be extremely meaningful to throw light on the socio-cultural context of its compilation.

Date Range: 1100 CE - 1400 CE

Region: Gujarat

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India, Gujarat

The map depicts present-day Gujarat.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Bharucha, Ervad Sheriarji Dadabhai. Collected Sanskrit Writings of the Parsis. Part II. – Ijnsi. Bombay, 1910.
- Source 2: Goldman, Leon. The Sanskrit Yasna Manuscript S1. Facsimile Edition. Handbook of Oriental Studies – Corpus Avesticum 32/1. Leiden - Boston: Brill, 2018.
- Source 3: Spiegel, Friedrich. Neriosengh's Sanskrit-Uebersetzung des Yaçna. Leipzig: Wilhelm Engelmann, 1861.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://eprints.soas.ac.uk/37213/>
- Source 1 Description: Palladino, Martina. PhD Thesis. The Sanskrit Version of Yasna 1-8. A Critical Edition with Commentaries and Glossary. SOAS University of London. 2021.
- Source 2 URL: <https://muya.soas.ac.uk/>
- Source 2 Description: Multimedia Yasna (MUYA) Project website.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://ada.geschkult.fu-berlin.de/>
- Source 1 Description: Avestan Digital Archive (ADA), where the digitised copies of some manuscripts containing the Sanskrit Yasna are available.
- Source 2 URL: gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b100885212
- Source 2 Description: Manuscript 674_P11, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Paris.
- Source 3 URL: gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b100883075
- Source 3 Description: Manuscript 660_P3, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Paris.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: The script adopted for the Sanskrit version of the Yasna is a peculiar type of Nāgarī, the so-called Parsi Nāgarī. It shares many features with Jaina Nāgarī, such as the way of writing conjunct consonants.

Reference: Goldman, Leon. The Sanskrit Yasna Manuscript S1. Facsimile Edition. Leiden - Boston: Brill, n.d..

Inked

– with Ink

Notes: The peculiarity of the manuscripts containing the Sanskrit version of the Yasna is that

they are generally bilingual, containing the Avestan original text followed by the Sanskrit corresponding passages. Avestan is written right to left, Sanskrit is written left to right. Therefore, to preserve the text flow and probably save some space, the Sanskrit text is written upside-down. To read the Sanskrit text, it is necessary to turn the folios upside-down and read the Sanskrit from the bottom to the top of the page.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Normal paper, probably handmade, bound in a book.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: A peculiar case is folio 68r of manuscript 672_K6, preserved at the library in Copenhagen: an original fragment by the famous scribe Mihrābān Kayhusraw, belonging to another text, was joined to the folio without any overwriting.

Reference: Cantera, Alberto. *Vers Une Édition De La Liturgie Longue Zoroastrienne: Pensées Et Travaux Préliminaires*. Paris, n.d.. p.147

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Notes: We find some corrections to the text in the manuscripts, but applied to the text after the writing. The correction replaces the first hand version. Sometimes the corrections are by the same hand, some others are clearly by a different hand (*secunda manu*).

Reference: Palladino, Martina. *The Sanskrit Version of Yasna 1-8. A Critical Edition with Commentaries and Glossary* (phd Thesis). SOAS University of London, n.d.. p.50

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: The manuscripts containing the Sanskrit version of the Yasna are preserved at different libraries and were part of private collections. They appear in catalogues and have been listed by Hintze (2012).

Reference: Hintze, Almut. "Manuscripts of the Yasna and Yasna Ī Rapithwin". Edited by Alberto Cantera. *The Transmission of the Avesta*. Iranica, no. 20 (n.d.).

Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

Notes: Manuscripts containing the Sanskrit version of the Yasna used to be part of private collections. Unfortunately, many of the manuscripts that belonged to private collections are now at unknown places. Bharucha in 1910 was able to use in his editions manuscripts that are now lost.

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: The extant manuscripts of the Sanskrit Yasna are preserved at the following libraries Kongelige Bibliotek, Copenhagen: ms. 672_K6, ms. 673_K15; Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris: ms. 660_P3, ms. 674_P11, Suppl. Pers. 1663-1664 (Burnouf 1); Bodleian Library, Oxford: ms. 671_J3; Rare Book and Manuscript Library, Columbia University, New York: ms. 677_S1; First Dastur Meherji Rana Library, Nāvsārī: ms. 680_T7, ms. 681_T55a; Ketābxāne-ye Melli, Tehrān: ms. 682_KM7; K R Cama Oriental Institute, Mumbai: 670_D96, 675_R245, R317.

↳ Specify

– Specify: Libraries or private residences. Since some extant manuscripts which were available at the beginning of the 20th century are now at unknown locations, there is still the hope that some of them may be found in the next years in some institutes or houses.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: The Yasna is a ritual text. Although the reason that lies behind the Sanskrit version is not clear and, among the many hypotheses, there is also the religious discourse with other communities at court, the translation of the Zoroastrian texts into Sanskrit were probably not funded by the polity. More probably, the same laymen who funded the copying of Zoroastrian Avestan and Pahlavi manuscripts were also supporting the copies of the Sanskrit version.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The original Avestan text, the Yasna, is one of the most important liturgies in Zoroastrianism. Its translations, and especially the Sanskrit version, does not bear the same ritual value.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: Avestan is the sacred language of the Parsis, and the Yasna was originally composed in Avestan. Sanskrit is in itself a sacred language in other Indian cults. However, in this context, the so-called Parsi Sanskrit is not considered a sacred language.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The aim of the translation into Sanskrit is still not clear to the scholarship, and therefore, the target audience cannot be estimated. Most probably, the Sanskrit Yasna was compiled to provide a sort of paraphrase to the Pahlavi version, which is the main source of the Sanskrit version. Moreover, at that time, all the Indian religious communities were going through a process of 'Sanskritisation' of their texts to reach out local courts and engage in a religious dialogue with other communities.

Reference: Palladino, Martina. The Sanskrit Version of Yasna 1-8. A Critical Edition with Commentaries and Glossary (phd Thesis). SOAS University of London, n.d.. p.28-32

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: The Parsi community is traditionally endogamic and close to the conversion of external members. The conversion and the so-called New Zoroastrianism is now a highly controversial theme in the community.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: The manuscripts include the Avestan text of the Yasna, which is the one recited in the ritual, followed by its Sanskrit translation and additional comments. The Sanskrit text in itself is not employed in the ritual practice.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: The text has no material significance. The Sanskrit version is not used for a ritual purpose, and therefore there is no material significance to the text. Moreover, even the Avestan original Yasna belongs to an oral tradition and the text is recited by heart during the ritual.

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

↳ Calligraphy?

– No

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: A few manuscripts include some graphic elements. In the manuscripts containing the Sanskrit Yasna, we often find graphic elements such as wheels, flowers and a four pointed diagram resembling a flower, very similar to a Jaina śrīvatsa. It is a symbology that belongs to Jaina iconography, and not to the Zoroastrian tradition.

Reference: Goldman, Leon. The Sanskrit Yasna Manuscript S1. Facsimile Edition. Leiden - Boston: Brill, n.d.. p.43-45

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: The Sanskrit text has been transmitted in a certain number of manuscripts, twenty-four in total according to the list of manuscripts included in the catalogues. Unfortunately, many of them are now lost. The text is very similar in all the manuscripts that are available today and were available in the past. Therefore, the text is one, and we only find minor variations attested in the different copies.

Reference: Hintze, Almut. "Manuscripts of the Yasna and Yasna Ī Rapithwin". Edited by Alberto Cantera. *The Transmission of the Avesta. Iranica*, no. 20 (n.d.).

Reference: Palladino, Martina. *The Sanskrit Version of Yasna 1-8. A Critical Edition with Commentaries and Glossary* (phd Thesis). SOAS University of London, n.d..

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: Other Zoroastrian text were translated into Sanskrit, namely some fragments of the Vīdēvdād, some Khorde Avesta texts, and other text originally composed in Pahlavi, such as the Ardā Wīrāz Nāmag, the Dādestān ī Mēnōg ī Xrad and the Škand Gumānīg Wizār.

Reference: Goldman, Leon. *The Sanskrit Yasna Manuscript S1. Facsimile Edition*. Leiden - Boston: Brill, n.d.. p.2

Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Notes: The Zoroastrian texts cannot really be considered a canon. Unlikely the canons of the other religious movements, the Avesta has never been formally canonised. The texts were written in different periods and in different languages; they were also arranged in a liturgical way rather than composing a canon.

Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Notes: The Sanskrit Yasna belongs to the translation of the Zoroastrian ritual or religious text, originally composed in Avestan and Pahlavi. Therefore, its literary tradition is linked to the scriptures, but it represent a translation into another language that serves no ritual purpose.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Notes: The Yasna is a liturgical text which includes many ritual aspects. We find lists of divine beings invited to the sacrifice, lists of ritual implements, etc. The Sanskrit version of the text provides the

Sanskrit equivalents of the ritual items.

Reference: Palladino, Martina. The Sanskrit Version of Yasna 1-8. A Critical Edition with Commentaries and Glossary (phd Thesis). SOAS University of London, n.d..

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: The Zoroastrian calendar which appears in the Avestan version of the Yasna is based on the Old Iranian luni-solar calendar. The year is composed by 12 months of 30 days. The Yasna liturgical manuscripts mention the dedication to the divinities of the day and the month in which the ceremony is performed. In the Sanskrit version, since the text was not used for a ritual purpose, the dedication is absent and supplied with ritual instructions in Sanskrit.

Reference: Palladino, Martina. The Sanskrit Version of Yasna 1-8. A Critical Edition with Commentaries and Glossary (phd Thesis). SOAS University of London, n.d.. p.73-74

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The spirit-body distinction is surely present in the text of the Yasna, but it is only outlined. The Yasna is a ritual text, and therefore, the supernatural elements, including the soulish components, are mentioned and praised. However, there is no extensive explanation of the spirit-body relation, which is explained in detail by the later Middle Persian exegesis.

Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: The animic/incorporeal part of the human beings survives after death and it is separate from the body. However, the body is not despised and, on the contrary, used as a mean to be on the side of good and fight evil.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: The Zoroastrian cult distinguishes two different levels of any terrestrial aspect, namely one 'material' and the other 'mental'. Those two concepts, already present in the Yasna text, were then further developed in the Middle Persian literature. In Sanskrit, the material

dimension is called pṛthvīcara- adj. 'moving on earth' or pṛthvīcārin- adj. 'living on earth', and the mental one is called paralokacārin- adj. 'living in the other world'.

Reference: Shaked, Shaul. "GĒTĪG AND MĒNŌG". Encyclopaedia Iranica Online, n.d.. http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2330-4804_EIRO_COM_2089.

Reference: Palladino, Martina. The Sanskrit Version of Yasna 1–8. A Critical Edition with Commentaries and Glossary (phd Thesis). SOAS University of London, n.d..

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

Notes: In the text of the Yasna there is no deeper analysis of the psyche, since it is a ritual text.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: The distinction between 'material' or 'corporal' and 'mental' is one of the most important concepts in the Zoroastrian beliefs. Therefore, it is also one of the main themes in exegesis and discussion.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

Notes: The dualism body-soul in Zoroastrianism is more articulated. In fact, there are many components of the human spiritual profile, namely the Avestan uruuan-, the daēnā- and the frauuaši-, and not a single spiritual element which separates from the body after death.

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: The animic or incorporeal parts of the human beings are mentioned in the Yasna, and the Sanskrit version provides its translation. These concepts, namely the Av. uruuan-, daēnā- and frauuaši-, are highly debated among scholars. They are incorporeal essences which in any case relate to the human sphere. In Sanskrit, they have been rendered as ātman- 'self', dīni- (loanword) and vr̥ḍdhi- 'prosperity' respectively. While uruuan- and frauuaši- have been translated with calques, i.e. a correspondent Sanskrit term is provided, dīni- is a loanword based on the Pahlavi form dēn. Those Zoroastrian concepts are highly debated among scholars; the Pahlavi literature further develops and describes those concepts, which are only mentioned at the earlier stage of the Yasna.

Reference: Shaki, Mansour. "DĒN". Encyclopaedia Iranica Online, n.d.. http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2330-4804_EIRO_COM_8311.

Reference: Boyce, Mary. "FRAVAŠĪ". Encyclopaedia Iranica Online, n.d..

http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2330-4804_EIRO_COM_1736.

Reference: Palladino, Martina. The Sanskrit Version of Yasna 1-8. A Critical Edition with Commentaries and Glossary (phd Thesis). SOAS University of London, n.d..

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

Notes: Notes: The later Middle Persian exegesis clarifies that men possess different spiritual components, namely the Avestan uruuan- (Sanskrit ātman-), the proper 'soul', and the Avestan daēnā- (Sanskrit dīni-), also a spiritual attribute of men, the 'inner self'. In the exegesis, the daēnā- is generally depicted as a beautiful woman, who after death is reunited with the male spiritual component, the uruuan-.

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– No

Notes: The Yasna is one of the most important Zoroastrian texts, recognised by all the branches of the Zoroastrian cult. The Sanskrit version of the Yasna does not have any ritual value and therefore, it does not belong to either a mainstream or a minority position. This text only represents a very interesting work of philology ante litteram.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text of the Yasna suggests the belief in afterlife and the surviving of the soul after death. However, those themes are only mentioned in the Yasna and further developed in later literature.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: In the Yasna we only find only the mention of afterlife spatial locations. For instance, the bridge cinuuat̄pərətu- (caṃdorapuhala- setu- in Sanskrit) is mentioned. It is the bridge that the soul has to cross after death to reach the other world. However, no further explanation is provided in the text of the Yasna.

Reference: Tafazzolī, Aḥmad. "ČINWAD PUHL". Encyclopaedia Iranica Online, n.d..
http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2330-4804_EIRO_COM_7728.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: Even in this case, it is only later literature which develops Zoroastrian eschatology and clarifies that the time is limited, and therefore, even afterlife will come to an end. The temporality of the afterlife is not mentioned in the Yasna.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: There is no belief of rebirth or reincarnation in Zoroastrianism.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: Burial practices are not mentioned in the text of the Yasna. However, Zoroastrians traditionally exposed corpses to carrion eating birds on the so-called 'towers of silence'.

Reference: Negahban, Ezzatollah, Frantz Grenet, James R. Russell, Hamid Algar, and Vahid Rafati. "BURIAL". Encyclopaedia Iranica Online, n.d.. http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2330-4804_EIRO_COM_7197.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: Formal burials are not present in the text. The Vīdēvdād, another Zoroastrian text, includes the burial practices.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Zoroastrian cult includes a high number of supernatural beings. They are good or evil and in a constant fight to dominate the world. The Yasna text mentions many different entities who are addressed in the ritual and called to defeat the evil ones. The names of the supernatural beings have been translated into Sanskrit, generally with loanwords coming from Pahlavi or from the original Avestan version. Moreover, the Sanskrit text includes some of the Pahlavi exegetical comments and adds new original Sanskrit comments. In those comments, which are not in any case as extended and detailed as the later literature, we find additional mention and attributes of divine entities.

A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: Ahura Mazdā is the supreme god of the Zoroastrian cult. In Sanskrit, his name appears as svāmin- mahājñānin- 'Lord of Great Wisdom'; it is also called ahuramajda-, a loanword based on the Avestan form, and hormmijda-, a loanword based on the Pahlavi form.

Reference: Palladino, Martina. The Sanskrit Version of Yasna 1-8. A Critical Edition with Commentaries and Glossary (phd Thesis). SOAS University of London, n.d.. p.107

Reference: Boyce, Mary. "AHURA MAZDĀ". Encyclopaedia Iranica Online, n.d..
http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2330-4804_EIRO_COM_4968.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: In the text of the Yasna we only find allusions to an anthropomorphic form. Some examples are: in Y. 31.3 his tongue, which in Sanskrit is *jihva-*, is mentioned; in 43.4, the Avestan *zasta-* 'hand', does not find a direct correspondence in Sanskrit, which is based on the Pahlavi version.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: We find an allusion to Ahura Mazda positioned in the sky in Y. 30.5; in the Sanskrit version we have the term *ākāśa-* 'sky, atmosphere'.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Notes: In Zoroastrianism, we do not find any identification or fusion of the monarch with any divine being. The monarch has the role of protecting and promoting the Zoroastrian cult.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

Notes: Only trained priests can celebrate the ritual to please Ahura Mazda. Every Zoroastrian is however entitled to pray to the divine entities. The Sanskrit version of the Yasna, even if it is in any case the product of a priestly environment, does not have any ritual or religious value.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god, Ahura Mazda, represents the forces of good, while his twin Angra Mainii stands for evil forces.

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Ahura Mazda has fire as his son and is accompanied by divine entities called Aməša Spəntas, called amara- guru(tara)- 'Immortal (More) Venerable Ones', amara-mahattara- 'Immortal Greater Ones' or with the loanword amiśāspiṃta- in Sanskrit.

Reference: Palladino, Martina. The Sanskrit Version of Yasna 1-8. A Critical Edition with Commentaries and Glossary (phd Thesis). SOAS University of London, n.d.. p.109

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Ahura Mazda is omniscient. In particular, in Y. 45.4 he is qualified as 'all-seeing', sarvajñānin 'the one who knows everything' in Sanskrit.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: Ahura Mazdā also knows the future of the world: at the end of time, his forces will defeat evil ones.

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Ahura Mazdā constantly fights evil forces and protects human beings.

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Notes: Ahura Mazdā is called to join the ritual to maintain the cosmic order. Therefore, he protects the human beings and gives them prosperity. In the Zoroastrian pantheon we also find Aši, a divine being who personifies the Reward. The corresponding terms in Sanskrit are the loanword arśiśa° and the calque puṇya- 'good'. The Reward is on the side of Ahura Mazdā, even if it is generally directly associated to another divinity, Sraoša.

↳ Can punish

– No

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: Ahura Mazdā is the primary cause of the world and claims direct efficacy. His constant and manifest presence also influences the human behaviour for the better.

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: Ahura Mazdā represents the source of good himself.

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Notes: The Zoroastrian pantheon is composed of a large number of supernatural beings and entities. Those who are on the side of Ahura Mazdā are invited to join the sacrifice and praised by human beings.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– *Specify:* The supreme high god Ahura Mazdā is identified with Spənta Maiīiiu 'Life-giving Force', the good twin spirit who opposes the evil twin Angra Maiīiiu. In Sanskrit, it is rendered with the loanword Spanāmainīo, based on the Pahlavi form.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– No

Notes: Ahura Mazdā does not communicate with living beings in any dialogical form. He communicated through Zarathustra, who taught the new religion. The supreme god accepts sacrifices offered through the ritual specialists' performances, listens to the prayers, and replies supporting mankind in many aspects of life.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Notes: The Avestan Yasna is a written version of a ritual text that has to be learned and recited by the priest to communicate to the high-god. The Sanskrit version does not have any ritual purpose.

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: There is a huge debate in scholarship about the Frauuaṣis, who are addressed in the Yasna as male and female. They have been identified with the souls of ancient heroes, as they support and

protect human beings especially in fights. The hymn dedicated to them is also generally associated to funerary rituals. The correspondent term in the Sanskrit version is vṛddhi- 'prosperity'.

Reference: Boyce, Mary. "FRAVAŠI". Encyclopaedia Iranica Online, n.d.. http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2330-4804_EIRO_COM_1736.

↳ Human spirits can be seen
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt
– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world
– Yes

Notes: The Frauuaṣis assist people and take care of the world.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

–Specify: They fly in the sky in huge number and look after human beings.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

Notes: They support mankind especially in relation to warlike activities, but they also grant offspring.

↳ Human spirits can punish

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: They are supportive and help mankind.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Notes: The communication takes place with human beings invoking and praising those spirits, who support them back.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Different supernatural beings are called to join the sacrifice in the text of the Yasna: the Yazatas, the divinities of the pantheon who deserve the sacrifice; the Aməša Spəntas, entities who are very close to Ahura Mazdā.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Many supernatural beings are supposed to be omniscient, but whether they possess future sight or not is not specified.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings constantly assist mankind. Each divinity generally takes care of a specific domain, and he/she is addressed according to the need of men.

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings reward human beings who invoke and sacrifice to them.

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– No

Notes: Even evil forces do not punish human beings because evil belongs to the 'mental' dimension. The fight against the evil forces is generally carried out by other divine beings who are on Ahura Mazda's side.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings accept sacrifices and prayers, and grant prosperity in return.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: Their intervention in the human world is generally intentional and manifest.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: The good divine beings and entities are helpful and supportive to mankind.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: The evil forces possess all the negative features and emotions.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: The good supernatural beings contribute to maintaining the cosmic order which was established by Ahura Mazdā.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

Notes: There are kin relationships between some supernatural entities, but not exclusively.

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Notes: Ahura Mazdā is the supreme god, the other divine beings come after him.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: Most of the supernatural beings are personifications of concepts and are therefore acting in a specific domain.

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: The Zoroastrian pantheon includes positive forces who are allied of Ahura Mazdā, but also evil forces, like Anra Mainiiu or the Daēvas, enemies of the gods.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: The human figures who are meaningful to the Zoroastrian cult, such as Zaratuštra, the Saošyant or even Gayōmart (Avestan gaya- marətan-), the primordial man, belong in any case to the human domain and are not supernatural beings.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings are invoked in the Yasna and invited to the sacrifice. The Sanskrit version follows the original text and invites the supernatural beings to join the sacrifice with equivalent expressions.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the text the supernatural beings are addressed with epithets and descriptions of their appearance and attributes.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: no

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In general, good supernatural beings care about a correct behaviour towards others to maintain the order.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: Mankind has to follow some rules and adhere to prosocial norms, and especially to respect truthfulness with 'good thoughts, good words and good deeds'. However, the final aim is to maintain the cosmic order and please the gods, above all Ahura Mazdā. In this sense, supernatural monitoring is helping the human social sphere, but more as an indirect effect of the religious duty.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual offerings are the core of the rituals to please the divine beings and ask for their help.

↳ Libations?

– Yes

Notes: Water libations are essential to the ritual. Water also purifies the sacred object used during the ritual.

↳ Food?

– Yes

Notes: The sacred bread is offered to the gods and ingested by the priest during the Yasna ritual.

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: Whether the animal sacrifice was performed or not is a debated matter in scholarship.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Sacred objects?

– Yes

Notes: Sacred objects are involved in the ritual and offered to the divine beings. For instance, the ritual bundle (Avestan *barəsman-*, Sanskrit *baresmana-*) is one of the most important ritual implements.

↳ Daily life objects?

– Yes

Notes: Daily life objects, such as wood and incense, bread or milk are offered in the ritual.

↳ Other?

–Specify: The sacred drink *para.haōma-* / *prāhūma-*, extracted from the plant of *haōma-* / *hūma-*, is offered during the ritual to please the gods.

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– No

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

Notes: The most sacred place, the fire temple, can be accessed only by Zoroastrians.

↳ Sacred object(s)

– Yes

Notes: The sacred implements used during the ritual have to be properly purified.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Yes

Notes: Some kind of animals are not well-accepted by Zoroastrians and presumably, by the good supernatural beings: the so-called xrafstra- animals, such as reptiles or insects, which are considered belonging to evil forces against Ahura Mazdā.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Notes: Any kind of evil action is condemned and against the forces of good.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

Notes: Good supernatural forces promote any vital impulse, including sex. Abstinence is considered a demoniac practice.

↳ Adultery

– No

↳ Incest

– Yes

Notes: Incestuous marriage was considered the best form of union, as Zoroastrian cosmogony, exposed in detail in later literature, is based on incest.

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– No

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: Lying is the worst offence to the good supernatural beings. The most important concept in Zoroastrianism is probably truth.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: 'Good thoughts, good words, and good deeds', one of the most important Zoroastrian concepts, implies that words are always followed by corresponding actions.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about vitality. Therefore, laziness is not a positive attitude.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: The text of the Yasna mentions sorcery as a demoniac practice.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
 - Notes: 'Good words' are especially meaningful in Zoroastrianism.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
 - Notes: Especially in the text of the Yasna, which is a ritual in itself, ritual observance is extremely important.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
 - Notes: Specialists have to perform the ritual in the correct way. For this reason, the Avestan alphabet includes numerous sounds which help in a punctual pronunciation of the words, and liturgical manuscripts include a good number of ritual instructions.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
 - Notes: Proselytism is not a traditional Zoroastrian practice.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
 - Notes: Fairness is a leading Zoroastrian virtue in all domains.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - Yes
 - Notes: The maintenance of places, and especially of sacred places such as the fire temple, is an important activity to show respect and please divine beings.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: Supernatural beings on the side of Ahura Mazda care about maintaining the order of the world and even mankind is called to support Ahura Mazda's activity.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: Even if it is not a real form of punishment, evil forces created by Angra Mainiu are present in the text; but they are defeated by the good forces of Ahura Mazda.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Notes: The Zoroastrian supernatural beings are invoked to join the ritual and reward mankind who praises them.

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: Any divine being can be generous with mankind.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Notes: Divine intervention is generally manifest.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Notes: Divine rewards anyway reinforce religious adherence.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

Notes: The enhancement of group norms is not the aim, but an indirect effect of following Zoroastrian principles.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: According to the person's behaviour and influence of the evil forces, he/she can be rewarded in the afterlife. The text of the Yasna, however, does not describe the afterlife; later Zoroastrian literature provides detailed descriptions.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

Notes: According to the Zoroastrian belief, afterlife is anyway a temporary state because Ahura Mazda's forces will defeat evil and end time. Afterlife rewards or punishments are temporary as well, and therefore, not particularly emphasised in the doctrine.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– No

Notes: Even positive afterlife is temporary. At the end of time, when Ahura Mazda will be victorious, a kind of Golden Age will be restored for everybody.

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

↳ Other?

– Yes

Notes: According to later eschatological literature, when the time will be over, Ahura Mazda will win over evil forces. Therefore, everybody will abandon even afterlife and a kind of Golden Age will be restored.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: Prayers and rituals are performed to ask for any kind of reward to the good supernatural beings.

↳ Highly emphasized?

– No

Notes: Rituals are performed to get rewards. However, the most important aspect consists in following the religious duty and Ahura Mazda's precepts.

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

Notes: One ritual time mentioned in the Yasna, Avestan *bərəjiiia-* 'belonging to esteem, esteem-', Sanskrit *bereji-*, is directly associated with the increase of grain's production by the Sanskrit original comment to the text.

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

–Specify: No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the text of the Avestan Yasna, the Saošyant is a helper whose semantics is still not clear at this earlier stage. It also appear in the plural form. In the Sanskrit version of the Yasna, the term is rendered as lābhat- (for instance, Y. 20.3) or lābhamat- (for instance, Y. 45.11, 46.3, 48.12, 53.2), present participles probably linked to the verb lābh- 'to direct'. In later eschatological texts it is identified with the saviour, one of Zarathustra's sons, who will come, end the time and restore a sort of Golden Age.

Reference: Malandra, William. "SAOŠYANT". Encyclopaedia Iranica Online, n.d..
http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2330-4804_EIRO_COM_11309.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: Saošyant cannot be considered a messiah because he will simply end a cycle. He will come at the end of time, when Ahura Mazdā's forces will defeat evil.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– No

Notes: Even if he cannot be consider a proper messiah, Saošyant will come to put an end to time and proclaim Ahura Mazdā's victory.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: The Yasna text does not include an explanation of the Zoroastrian eschatology. Therefore, the Sanskrit version does not include it as well. Later Pahlavi texts illustrate the fascinating Zoroastrian eschatology.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not include any social norms because it is the text of a liturgy and not a code listing religious or social rules. The Vīdēvdād represents such kind of code in the Zoroastrian cult.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: There is no distinction between conventional and moral values in the text. The sacrifice, which in any case loses its effectiveness in its Sanskrit version, is regulated by ritual norms; moral precepts are not implied here.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Notes: The most important Zoroastrian value is truthfulness, but this not necessarily implies a moral aspect. Even in one of the most famous Zoroastrian precepts, 'good words, good thoughts, good deeds', 'good' means 'conforming to the order', following the rules of the Zoroastrian religion. Any virtue is praised, but not from a moral point of view.

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Notes: Righteousness is not perceived as a virtue, but a behaviour which consists in acting properly according to the Zoroastrian beliefs, i.e. following the rules.

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: Ritual purity is essential to officiating priests; Zoroastrian have long purification rituals which take place before solemn rites.

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

Notes: The most important aspect for an observant Zoroastrian is to strictly follow the religious rules.

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

Notes: Perceived as health and solidity.

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Notes: A Zoroastrian knows that in the end Ahura Mazda will be victorious and therefore, Zoroastrian is in general a positive and optimistic doctrine.

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Notes: Especially towards rewards granted by Ahura Mazda and the other good supernatural beings.

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: Any qualities that can stimulate vital instincts such as desire are praised.

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Any vital and active virtues which help maintaining the cosmic order please Ahura Mazda and the other divinities.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: On the contrary, sexual abstinence is considered an evil practice by Zoroastrianism, which promotes any vital and reproductive instinct.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: Zoroastrian are in general against any deprivation of the vital impulses. During the Yasna ritual, the consecrated bread is ingested by the chief priest.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: Zoroastrians do not have any food restrictions.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The text of the Yasna originally includes prayers which have to be repeated and ritual instructions. However, the Sanskrit text has never been performed as a ritual.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: The Sanskrit version is not recited in any kind of rite. On the contrary, any performance of a ritual includes a physical risk; in fact, if the ritual is not performed in the correct way, it may cause disgrace and physical injuries for the performer or the commissioner.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires the embracement of truthfulness, rectitude and order, but in a rather religious than ethical way.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: Even if the Sanskrit text is not used in the ritual, the private ritual sphere and prayers are very important in a Zoroastrian's life.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 5

Notes: According to the Yasna text and its Sanskrit version, the times of the sacrifice are five a day, during day- and night-time.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: The text is itself the record of a solemn Zoroastrian ritual in Avestan with its corresponding Sanskrit version.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The Yasna is a ritual text and therefore, it does not include any extra-ritual elements. On a general level, a Parsi extra-ritual marker used to be the Parsi Gujarati language, a specific form of Gujarati spoken by the Parsi community. However, the use of this language has rapidly decreased and nowadays, only a very limited number of people, often aged ones, can still speak it.

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Notes: The kinship terminology is used for divine beings. For instance, the fire is called Ahura Mazda's son.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

Notes: It generally applies to divine entities.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– Yes

Notes: The kinship terminology is not abundant in the text.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

Notes: The text of the Avestan Yasna is ritual and has a specific purpose. The Sanskrit Yasna does not have a ritual purpose and therefore, even if the reason behind its compilation is not clear, was in any case a divertissement or an example of philology ante litteram.

↳ Drama?

– No

↳ Comedy?

– No

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text of the Yasna is the guide to the performance of a sacrifice. Libations and food offerings are included, as well as specific ritual objects.

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: Whether Zoroastrians practiced animal sacrifice is still a debated topic in scholarship. Zoroastrianism seems to reject violence; however, we cannot exclude that animal sacrifice took place in the ancient ritual. In the text of the Yasna itself, we find the offering of the cow *baōiriia-* (Sanskrit *bavara-*, a loanword), which has been later interpreted as the cow's meet. Moreover, Zoroastrians are not vegetarian and do not have any meat taboo.

Reference: Redard, Céline. *The Srōš Drōn – Yasna 3 to 8. A Critical Edition with Ritual Commentaries and Glossary*. Leiden - New York: Brill, n.d.. p.103

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Notes: There is no concrete evidence of human sacrifice in the Zoroastrian ritual.

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: The offerings are part of Avestan ritual. The Sanskrit equivalents are present in the Sanskrit Yasna text.

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– No

Notes: The offered objects are not valuable from an economic point of view.

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Notes: Wood, incense, milk, bread are offered and used during the Yasna ceremony. The Sanskrit version also includes the Sanskrit corresponding terms.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

Notes: Incense is burnt and fragrance spread.

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: One of the most important offerings is the haōma, the sacred plant with which the para.haōma juice is made. In Parsi Sanskrit, they are rendered as hūma- and prāhūma-.

Notes: All the offerings and ritual objects must be purified with water and prayers.

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

Notes: The priests who perform the ritual are the only ones admitted in the sacred precinct.

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Notes: Liturgical Avestan manuscripts of the Yasna ritual also include ritual instructions which also involve the display of the sacred precinct. In the Sanskrit version, we have a few ritual instructions, which however, do not provide any information on the display or maintenance of the sacred space.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Translators into Sanskrit probably belonging to a priestly environment. The people who compiled the Sanskrit version of the Yasna had a very good knowledge of Avestan, Pahlavi and Sanskrit language. Moreover, they were familiar with the Zoroastrian ritual and other Indian cults, whose significant terms are mentioned in the Sanskrit Yasna.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Patrons who were paying the scribes to copy the text in new manuscripts.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Nobody destroyed the text. Unfortunately, many manuscripts containing the Sanskrit Yasna have been lost, but this has not been intentional. They were part of private collections and did not become part of any institute's collection.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Notes: The Avestan text of the Yasna is still taught at the Dadar Athornan Institute in Mumbai, the only functioning Zoroastrian priestly training school. The Sanskrit version does not have any teaching purpose.

Reference: Daruwalla, Kerman. "Training of the Priests". The Multimedia Yasna, n.d..
<https://muya.soas.ac.uk/training-of-the-priests/>.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: There is no specific mention of restrictions in the text.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The Sanskrit version is the product of a priestly environment, but it is not taught.

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: There is no specific mention of restrictions, but the officiating priests are male.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: Once again, there is no specific mention of restrictions, but priesthood involves only the male gender. Obviously, women can study the texts, pray, but not officiate.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: The text does not mention any concrete aspect of warfare. However, the constant battle between good and evil forces to maintain the order in the world is frequently mentioned.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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